

Backward Kolmogorov Formulation of Neutron Branching Random Walk in Lattice Domains

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ABSTRACT

We describe a branching random walk model in a discrete domain that models the diffusion of neutrons in a homogeneous multiplicative medium with absorbing boundary conditions. We derive the discrete-state backward Kolmogorov equation for the generating function that describes the total number of particles in the domain, and we show the partial difference equations for the expectation and variance. Analytical solutions for a rectangular parallepiped geometry are discussed and verified using Monte Carlo simulations. It is shown that as the lattice size and time step go to zero the model recovers the advection-diffusion equation with known formulas for its drift and diffusion coefficients.

Keywords: Branching Process, Markov Processes, Monte Carlo, Generating Function, Diffusion

1. INTRODUCTION

The description of the neutron population in nuclear reaction chains is usually done by means of the Boltzmann neutron transport equation, which describes the time-evolution of the neutron density over the reactor domain. This approach relies on the assumption that a large number of particles is present in the medium, so the stochastic nature of reaction chains can be neglected [1]. Such an assumption however may not be true in the context of the reactor start-up. During these regimes concepts such as the probability of initiation or extinction probability take over deterministic concepts [2].

A complementary approach is possible through the theory of branching processes [3, 4]. In such models, the stochastic behavior of neutron populations are described by time evolution probability equations, which are formulated from assumptions over the Markovian nature of the reacting chains. The space dependence is generally characterized by the position of the initial reacting particle, and the process is seen as a superposition of the independent histories of particles evolving from the initial configuration [4, 5]. It is then common to study the generating functions from which the expectation and variance of the process are recovered as first and second moments, respectively.

The book by Pázsit and Pál [4] presents a one-dimensional branching process model in a discrete lattice domain which mimics the neutron transport problem considered in [6]. In the same spirit, the current work presents a 3D discrete lattice model based on the branching random walk of particles as an attempt to reproduce the diffusion of neutrons in a multiplicative domain. We analyze the model by means of a set of discrete state backward Kolmogorov equations for the generating function, which are constructed based on the rules of the dynamics of the process. It leads to the derivation of equations for the expectancy and variance of the total number of particles. Such a formulation in discrete domains offers the possibility of verification of the results through a synchronous Monte Carlo algorithm, where neutrons are grouped into generations and all particles evolve simultaneously at each iteration. We also show that this discrete model exhibits the continuous advection-diffusion equation limit, from which the resulting drift and diffusion constants are established.

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2. BRANCHING RANDOM WALK

In this section, a branching random walk model is presented in a lattice domain $\mathbb{D} \subset \mathbb{Z}^3$ with particles walking along the canonical directions $e_j \in \{(1, 0, 0), (-1, 0, 0), (0, 1, 0), (0, -1, 0), (0, 0, 1), (0, 0, -1)\}$, each with probability p_j . The process evolves in the discrete time $t \in \mathbb{N}_+$ under the following rules:

0. **Initial Condition:** The process starts with one neutron at position $r_0 \in \mathbb{D}$.
1. **Reaction:** Each neutron reacts with probability σ_R and disappears producing a random number of k new neutrons chosen with probability $\psi_k^{(1)}$, as well as a random number of n_i type- i precursors $i \in \{2, \dots, N + 1\}$ which are chosen with probabilities $\psi_{n_i}^{(i)}$. At time $t + 1$, each precursor particle remains in the original cell, while the k other neutron particles travel to cell $r + e_j$ with probability p_j .
2. **Scattering:** If a neutron does not react with probability $\sigma_S = 1 - \sigma_R$, then it travels at time $t + 1$ to cell $r + e_j$ chosen with probability p_j .
3. **Precursor decay:** Each precursor nuclide decays with probability $\lambda^{(i)}$ emitting a single neutron which at time $t + 1$ travels to cell $r + e_j$ with probability p_j .
4. **Boundary Condition:** Particles at positions outside the domain are absorbed and don't induce further reactions.

In the current work verification is done using Monte Carlo simulations with 1000 repetitions performed in a cube domain of size $L = L_x = L_y = L_z = 5$. Isotropy assumption is made through the simulations, with the transition probabilities $p_j = 1/2d$ along canonical directions, with $d = 3$ as the problem dimension. The offspring parameters are chosen purely for numerical purposes:

	ψ_0	ψ_1	ψ_2	ψ_3	ψ_4	ψ_5	ψ_6	ν	ξ	λ
Neutron	0.01	0.10	0.20	0.25	0.20	0.11	0.13	3.38	10.4	0.0
Precursor 1	0.70	0.30	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.30	0.0	0.002
Precursor 2	0.80	0.20	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.20	0.0	0.004
Precursor 3	0.99	0.01	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.01	0.0	0.008

Table I. Neutron and precursor offspring parameters for neutron induced reaction.

2.1. Generating Function Equation

Definition 1. The probability $\psi_k^{(i)}$ that a neutron emits k other particles from group $i \in \{1, \dots, N + 1\}$ has an offspring generating function $\Psi^{(i)}(s) := \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} \psi_k^{(i)} s^k$, $|s| \leq 1$. The first and second moments of the offspring generating function are denoted receptively by $\nu^{(i)} := \Psi'^{(i)}(1)$, $\xi^{(i)} := \Psi''^{(i)}(1)$.

Definition 2. The probability $p_k^{(i)}(t, r_0)$ that k particles are found in the domain at time t given that the process started at position r_0 with an initial particle from group $i \in \{1, \dots, N + 1\}$, has a generating function $G^{(i)}(t, r_0; s) := \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} p_k^{(i)}(t, r_0) s^k$, $|s| \leq 1$.

The generating function for the number of neutron particles at time t given the process started at cell r_0 can be constructed using combinatorial and Markovian arguments as shown in [4]. Extending the arguments for a discrete domain with N groups of unstable precursors and defining the convex sum $\bar{G}(t, r) := \sum_{j=1}^{2d} p_j G(t, r + e_j; s)$, one finds the generating function recurrence equation

$$G^{(1)}(t + 1, r_0; s) = \sigma_R \Psi^{(1)} \left(\bar{G}^{(1)}(t, r_0; s) \right) \prod_{i=2}^{N+1} \Psi^{(i)} \left(G^{(i)}(t, r_0; s) \right) + \sigma_S \bar{G}^{(1)}(t, r_0; s) \quad (1)$$

$$G^{(i)}(t+1, r_0; s) = \lambda^{(i)} \bar{G}^{(1)}(t, r_0; s) + (1 - \lambda^{(i)}) G^{(i)}(t, r_0; s), \quad \forall i \in \{2, 3, \dots, N+1\} \quad (2)$$

$$G^{(1)}(0, r_0; s) = s, \quad G^{(i)}(0, r_0; s) = 1, \quad r_0 \in \mathbb{D} \quad (3)$$

$$G^{(i)}(t, r_0; s) = 1, \quad \forall r_0 \notin \mathbb{D}, \quad \forall i \in \{1, 2, \dots, N+1\} \quad (4)$$

Eq. (1) states that the probability distribution of the neutron population at time $t+1$ given the original neutron particle started at position r_0 is the result of the evolution of two possible events that outcomes from the original particle: scattering with probability σ_S and fission with probability σ_R .

The scattering term $\sigma_S \bar{G}$ represents the probability distribution where the original neutron was scattered to the neighboring cells, with the process evolving as if it was the starting particle in the new cell. For the fission, the dynamics is again time-homogeneous and Markovian so each of the new neutrons is a start of an independent process at the respective site. The generating functions then multiply, resulting in $\sigma_R \Psi^{(1)}(\bar{G}^{(1)}(t, r_0, s)) \prod_{i=2}^{N+1} \Psi^{(i)}(G^{(i)}(t, r_0, s))$. Note that the pure absorption event is counted as the reaction where no new particles are produced with probability $\sigma_R \psi_0$.

Eq. (2) expresses the decay of precursors. If a precursor particle does not decay with probability $1 - \lambda^{(i)}$, it stays in the same place. If it decays, then the single neutron travels to the neighboring cell.

Eq. (3) states that the process starts from a single neutron particle at position r_0 , while Eq. (4) states that any particle that escape or start the process outside the domain is absorbed and then the neutron population stays at 0 with probability $p_0(t, r_0) = 1, \quad \forall r_0 \notin \mathbb{D}$.

Together Eqs (1)–(4) are a set of coupled non-linear partial difference equations. These do not provide a spatial description of the neutron population often found in reactor physics works such as [1]. Instead, they describe the total neutron population in the domain as a function of the position of the original particle. Although an analytical solution may be of little value, it's first and second moments are of direct significance since they carry information on the expectation and variance of the process respectively.

2.2. Expectation

Definition 3. The average numbers of particles emitted in a single neutron interaction per generation are denoted by $\bar{\nu}^{(i)} := \sigma_R \nu^{(i)}$ for $i > 1$ and $\bar{\nu}^{(1)} := \sigma_R \nu^{(1)} + (1 - \sigma_R)$.

The expected number of particles in the domain $\mu(t, r_0)$ can be recovered from the first derivative generating function $\partial_s G(t, r_0, s)|_{s=1}$. Applying ∂_s to Eqs (1)–(4) leads to a system of linear partial difference equations

$$\begin{cases} \mu^{(1)}(t+1, r_0) = \bar{\nu}^{(1)} \bar{\mu}^{(1)}(t, r_0) + \sum_{i=2}^{N+1} \bar{\nu}^{(i)} \mu^{(i)}(t, r_0) \\ \mu^{(i)}(t+1, r_0) = \lambda^{(i)} \bar{\mu}^{(1)}(t, r_0) + (1 - \lambda^{(i)}) \mu^{(i)}(t, r_0) \\ \mu^{(1)}(0, r_0) = 1, \quad \mu^{(i)}(0, r_0) = 0, \quad r_0 \in \mathbb{D} \\ \mu^{(i)}(t, r_0) = 0, \quad \forall i \in \{1, 2, \dots, N+1\}, \quad \forall r_0 \notin \mathbb{D}. \end{cases} \quad (5)$$

Consider a solution of the kind $\mu^{(i)}(t, r_0) = T^{(i)}(t)R(r_0)$, $R(r_0) = X(x)Y(y)Z(z)$. Substituting and rearranging, one finds

$$\frac{T^{(1)}(t+1) - \sum_{i=2}^{N+1} \bar{\nu}^{(i)} T^{(i)}(t)}{\bar{\nu}^{(1)} T^{(1)}(t)} = \frac{\bar{R}(r_0)}{R(r_0)} = \alpha_k, \quad \frac{T^{(i)}(t+1) - (1 - \lambda^{(i)}) T^{(i)}(t)}{\lambda^{(i)} T^{(1)}(t)} = \frac{\bar{R}(r_0)}{R(r_0)} = \alpha_k$$

The eigen-pairs $(\alpha_k, R_k(r_0))$ are given by

$$\alpha_k = \frac{1}{3} (\cos(\phi_x) + \cos(\phi_y) + \cos(\phi_z)), \quad R_k(r_0) = C_k \sin(x_0 \phi_x) \sin(y_0 \phi_y) \sin(z_0 \phi_z), \quad \phi_{x,y,z} = \frac{k_{x,y,z} \pi}{L_{x,y,z} + 1} \quad (6)$$

Figure 1. Evolution of the expected number of particles at critical regime. The left plot shows a comparison between Monte Carlo simulations with the recurrence solution of Eq. (5) for the total number of particles in the domain. The right plot shows a comparison between the recurrence solution with the analytical solution given by Eq. (9) for the evolution of the neutron histories distributed in space by the initial condition at positions $x_0 \in \{0, 1, \dots, L + 1\}$, $y_0 = 3$, $z_0 = 3$.

with $k = (k_x, k_y, k_z) \in \{1, \dots, L_x\} \times \{1, \dots, L_y\} \times \{1, \dots, L_z\} = K$. The recurrence in time is given by the set of equations

$$T_k^{(1)}(t + 1) = \alpha_k \bar{v}^{(1)} T_k^{(1)}(t) + \sum_{i=2}^{N+1} \bar{v}^{(i)}(t) T_k^{(i)}(t), \quad T_k^{(i)}(t + 1) = \alpha_k \lambda^{(i)} T_k^{(1)}(t) + (1 - \lambda^{(i)}) T_k^{(i)}(t), \quad (7)$$

which can be written in a matrix form $\mathbf{T}_k(t + 1) = \mathbf{A}_k \mathbf{T}_k(t)$ where

$$\mathbf{A}_k = \begin{bmatrix} \alpha_k \bar{v}^{(1)} & \bar{v}^{(2)} & \dots & \bar{v}^{(N+1)} \\ \alpha_k \lambda^{(2)} & 1 - \lambda^{(2)} & \dots & 0 \\ \vdots & \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ \alpha_k \lambda^{(N+1)} & 0 & \dots & 1 - \lambda^{(N+1)} \end{bmatrix}, \quad \mathbf{T}_k(t) = \begin{bmatrix} T_k^{(1)}(t) \\ \vdots \\ T_k^{(N+1)}(t) \end{bmatrix}. \quad (8)$$

The solution in the vector form is therefore a sine series

$$\boldsymbol{\mu}(t, r_0) = \sum_{k \in K} \mathbf{A}_k^t \mathbf{C}_k \sin(\phi_x x_0) \sin(\phi_y y_0) \sin(\phi_z z_0), \quad \boldsymbol{\mu}(t, r_0) = \begin{bmatrix} \mu^{(1)}(t, r_0) \\ \vdots \\ \mu^{(N+1)}(t, r_0) \end{bmatrix}. \quad (9)$$

The Fourier coefficients \mathbf{C}_k are found from the initial condition,

$$\mathbf{C}_k = \frac{8}{(L_x + 1)(L_y + 1)(L_z + 1)} \sum_{x_0=1}^{L_x} \sum_{y_0=1}^{L_y} \sum_{z_0=1}^{L_z} \boldsymbol{\mu}(0, r_0) \sin(\phi_x x_0) \sin(\phi_y y_0) \sin(\phi_z z_0). \quad (10)$$

The asymptotic behavior of $\boldsymbol{\mu}(t, r_0)$ is governed by the dominant eigenvalue of matrix \mathbf{A}_k . Define $\alpha = \max_{k \in K} \rho(\mathbf{A}_k)$ as the biggest spectral radius of the matrices \mathbf{A}_k . The criticality condition is given by

$$\alpha \sum_{i=1}^{N+1} \bar{v}^{(i)} = \alpha \bar{v} = 1, \quad (11)$$

where $\bar{\nu}$ represents the average number of particles produced at each generation by a fission reaction. Eq. (11) can also be derived from the steady state solution of Eq. (5). In the particular case of the cubic geometry, it becomes

$$\cos\left(\frac{\pi}{L+1}\right) \left[\sigma_R \left(\sum_{i=1}^{N+1} \nu^{(i)} - 1 \right) \right] = 1. \quad (12)$$

The criticality Eq. (12) asserts that regardless of the initial configuration, the average neutron population asymptotically approaches a steady state if parameters $(L, \sigma_R, \nu^{(i)})$ satisfy the relation. For the simulation of a transient scenario, the critical reaction probability is found $\sigma_R \approx 0.0535$ by solving Eq. (12) under the material parameters from Table I. A comparison between the analytical solution with Monte Carlo simulations and recurrence solutions are shown in Figure 1.

A formulation in discrete space and time domain is of particular significance when regarding computational costs and numerical implementations. Iterating Eq. (5) yields an exact solution, thus eliminating difficulties regarding error truncation typical from continuous formulations. It also brings the benefit of investigating the stability of particle populations as an analysis of convergence and stability of numerical sequences. In this approach the criticality conditions correspond to the stability conditions for numerical solutions of partial differential equations [7].

2.3. Variance

The variance for the number of particles in the domain is given by the relation

$$\sigma^2(t, r_0) = \eta(t, r_0) + \mu(t, r_0) - \mu(t, r_0)^2, \quad (13)$$

where $\mu(t, r_0)$ is the solution of equation (5) and $\eta(t, r_0)$ represents the second moment of the population distribution which we can obtain from $\eta(t, r_0) = \partial_{ss} G(t, r_0, s)|_{s=1}$. So, by differentiating the generating function equations (1)–(4) twice, we find the forced partial difference equation for the second moment

$$\begin{cases} \eta^{(1)}(t+1, r_0) = \bar{\nu}^{(1)} \bar{\eta}^{(1)}(t, r_0) + \sum_{i=2}^{N+1} \bar{\nu}^{(i)} \eta^{(i)}(t, r_0) + f(t, r_0) \\ \eta^{(i)}(t+1, r_0) = \lambda^{(i)} \bar{\eta}^{(1)}(t, r_0) + (1 - \lambda^{(i)}) \eta^{(i)}(t, r_0), \quad \forall i \in \{2, \dots, N+1\} \\ \eta^{(i)}(0, r_0) = 0, \quad \forall r_0 \in \mathbb{D}, \quad \eta^{(i)}(t, r_0) = 0, \quad \forall r_0 \notin \mathbb{D}, \quad \forall i \in \{1, \dots, N+1\} \end{cases} \quad (14)$$

where the force term $f(t, r_0)$ is given by

$$\begin{aligned} f(t, r_0) = & \sigma_R \bar{\zeta}^{(1)} \bar{\mu}^{(1)}(t, r_0)^2 + 2\nu^{(1)} \bar{\mu}^{(1)}(t, r_0) \sum_{i=2}^{N+1} \nu^{(i)} \mu^{(i)}(t, r_0) \\ & + \sum_{i=2}^{N+1} \sigma_R \bar{\zeta}^{(i)} \mu^{(i)}(t, r_0)^2 + \sum_{\substack{i, i'=2 \\ i \neq i'}}^{N+1} \sigma_R \nu^{(i)} \nu^{(i')} \mu^{(i)}(t, r_0) \mu^{(i')}(t, r_0). \end{aligned} \quad (15)$$

Eq. (14) is a partial difference equation with a forcing term which can be solved through a discrete sine transform. Define

$$\hat{\eta}_k^{(i)}(t) := \sum_{x_0=1}^{L_x} \sum_{y_0=1}^{L_y} \sum_{z_0=1}^{L_z} \eta^{(i)}(t, x_0, y_0, z_0) \sin(\phi_x x_0) \sin(\phi_y y_0) \sin(\phi_z z_0). \quad (16)$$

From basic trigonometric relations together with the isotropy assumption $p = 1/2d$ one gets

$$\sum_{x_0=1}^{L_x} \sum_{y_0=1}^{L_y} \sum_{z_0=1}^{L_z} \bar{\eta}^{(1)}(t, r_0) \sin(\phi_x x_0) \sin(\phi_y y_0) \sin(\phi_z z_0) = \alpha_k \hat{\eta}^{(1)}(t). \quad (17)$$

Figure 2. Evolution of the variance for the total number of particles in the domain at critical regime. The left plot shows a comparison between the analytical solution given by Eq. (20) and Monte Carlo simulations with data from Table I. The right plot compares the neutron population variance between recurrences of Eq.(14) using the reference nuclide (parameters in Table I) and a virtual nuclide with $\psi_3^{(1)} = 0.62$, $\psi_4^{(1)} = 0.38$, found by solving Eq. (21)

This leads to the set of space-independent equations

$$\hat{\eta}^{(1)}(t+1) = \bar{\nu}^{(1)} \alpha_k \hat{\eta}(t) + \sum_{i=2}^{N+1} \bar{\nu}^{(i)} \hat{\eta}^{(i)}(t) + \hat{f}(t), \quad \hat{\eta}^{(i)}(t) = \lambda^{(i)} \alpha_k \hat{\eta}(t) + (1 - \lambda^{(i)}) \hat{\eta}^{(i)}(t). \quad (18)$$

Recalling that \mathbf{A}_k is given by Eq. (8), the problem in matrix form becomes a simple recurrence with known solution

$$\hat{\eta}_k(t+1) = \mathbf{A}_k \hat{\eta}_k(t) + \mathbf{f}_k(t) \implies \hat{\eta}_k(t) = \sum_{\tau=0}^{t-1} \mathbf{A}_k^{t-\tau-1} \mathbf{f}_k(\tau), \quad \hat{\eta}_k(t) = \begin{bmatrix} \hat{\eta}_k^{(1)}(t) \\ \vdots \\ \hat{\eta}_k^{(N+1)}(t) \end{bmatrix}, \quad \mathbf{f}_k(t) = \begin{bmatrix} \hat{f}_k(t) \\ \vdots \\ 0 \end{bmatrix}. \quad (19)$$

Thus the final solution reads

$$\eta(t, r_0) = \frac{8}{(L_x + 1)(L_y + 1)(L_z + 1)} \sum_{k_x=1}^{L_x} \sum_{k_y=1}^{L_y} \sum_{k_z=1}^{L_z} \hat{\eta}_k(t) \sin(\phi_x x_0) \sin(\phi_y y_0) \sin(\phi_z z_0). \quad (20)$$

A consequence of this formula is that since at critical regime the forcing term $\mathbf{f}_k(t)$ converges and the dominant eigenvalue is $\alpha = 1$, then the second moment $\eta(t, r_0)$ and the variance diverge. This can be mitigated by minimizing the forcing term in Eq. (15) with respect to the second moment $\zeta^{(i)}$ constants. In this scenario we can perform simulations with a "virtual fissile material" with same multiplicity parameters $\nu^{(i)}$, where the offspring probabilities are optimized according to the problem:

$$\zeta^{(i)} = \min_{\{\psi_k^{(i)}\}_{k=0}^K} \sum_{k=2}^K k(k-1) \psi_k^{(i)} \quad \text{s.t.} \quad \sum_{k=1}^K k \psi_k^{(i)} = \nu^{(i)}, \quad \sum_{k=0}^K \psi_k^{(i)} = 1, \quad 0 \leq \psi_k^{(i)} \leq 1. \quad (21)$$

3. THE PASSAGE TO THE CONTINUOUS LIMIT

The current chapter investigate the passage of the previous model to the continuous limit. A standard limit procedure can be found in the work of [8] for a random walk case. Similarly, define the probability

densities Q_R, Q_S

$$p_R = dtQ_R + o(dt), \quad p_S = dtQ_S + o(dt), \quad (22)$$

as the probability that one interaction of reaction and scattering type respectively happens in a small interval of time dt . Also define $dt\lambda^{(n)} + o(dt)$ as the probability that one neutron particle is produced by the decay of an unstable nuclide of group $i \in \{2, \dots, N+1\}$ during the interval of time dt . Then we have

$$G^{(1)}(t+dt, r_0; s) = dtQ_R \Psi^{(1)}(\bar{G}^{(1)}(t, r_0; s)) \prod_{i=2}^{N+1} \Psi^{(i)}(G^{(i)}(t, r_0; s)) + dtQ_S \bar{G}^{(1)}(t, r_0; s) + o(dt), \quad (23)$$

$$G^{(i)}(t+dt, r_0; s) = dt\lambda^{(i)} \bar{G}^{(1)}(t, r_0; s) + (1 - dt\lambda^{(i)})G^{(i)}(t, r_0; s) + o(dt), \quad (24)$$

where

$$\bar{G}^{(1)}(t, r_0; s) = \sum_{j=1}^{2d} p_j G^{(1)}(t, r_0 + dr_j, s), \quad dr_j = e_j dx_j. \quad (25)$$

If $G^{(i)}$ are all analytical functions, we have the Taylor expansion

$$G^{(i)}(t+dt, r_0; s) = G^{(i)}(t, r_0; s) + dt\partial_t G^{(i)}(t, r_0; s) + o(dt^2), \quad (26)$$

$$G^{(1)}(t, r_0 + dr_j; s) = G^{(1)}(t, r_0; s) + \nabla G^{(1)}(t, r_0; s) \cdot dr_j + \frac{1}{2} dr_j \cdot (H[G^{(1)}] dr_j) + o(dr^3), \quad (27)$$

where $H[G]$ represents the hessian matrix. Then

$$\bar{G}^{(1)}(t, r_0; s) = \sum_{j=1}^{2d} p_j G^{(1)}(t, r_0; s) + \sum_{j=1}^{2d} p_j dr_j \cdot \nabla G^{(1)}(t, r_0; s) + \frac{1}{2} \sum_{j=1}^{2d} p_j dr_j \cdot (H[G^{(1)}] dr_j) + o(dr^3). \quad (28)$$

Since dr_j represents the projection of vector (dx, dy, dz) over the canonical directions, the terms on the right can be simplified to

$$\sum_{j=1}^{2d} p_j G^{(1)} = G^{(1)}, \quad \sum_{j=1}^{2d} p_j dr_j \cdot \nabla G^{(1)} = a \cdot \nabla G^{(1)}, \quad \frac{1}{2} \sum_{j=1}^{2d} p_j dr_j \cdot (H[G^{(1)}] dr_j) = b \cdot \nabla^2 G^{(1)}(t, r_0, s), \quad (29)$$

where \tilde{p}_j represents the probability associated with direction $-e_j$ and

$$a := (dx_0(p_x - \tilde{p}_x), dy_0(p_y - \tilde{p}_y), dz_0(p_z - \tilde{p}_z)), \quad b := \frac{1}{2} (dx_0^2(p_x + \tilde{p}_x), dy_0^2(p_y + \tilde{p}_y), dz_0^2(p_z + \tilde{p}_z)). \quad (30)$$

Substituting, the Taylor expansions leads to

$$G^{(1)} + dt\partial_t G^{(1)} + o(dt^2) = dtQ_R \Psi^{(1)}(\bar{G}^{(1)}) \prod_{i=2}^{N+1} \Psi^{(i)}(G^{(i)}) + dtQ_S (G^{(1)} + a \cdot \nabla G^{(1)} + b \cdot \nabla^2 G^{(1)}) + o(dr^3) \quad (31)$$

Rearranging these equations and recalling that for small dt one has $dtQ_R + dtQ_S \approx 1$, we get

$$dt\partial_t G^{(1)} + o(dt^2) = dtQ_R \left[\Psi^{(1)}(\bar{G}) \prod_{i=2}^{N+1} \Psi^{(i)}(G^{(i)}) - G^{(1)} \right] + dtQ_S (a \cdot \nabla G^{(1)} + b \cdot \nabla^2 G^{(1)}) + o(dr^3) \quad (32)$$

which in the limit $dt \rightarrow 0, dr^3/dt \rightarrow 0$ becomes the continuous diffusion equation

$$\partial_t G^{(1)}(t, r_0; s) = Q_R \left[\prod_{i=1}^{N+1} \Psi^{(i)}(G^{(i)}(t, r_0; s)) - G^{(1)}(t, r_0; s) \right] + C \cdot \nabla G^{(1)}(t, r_0; s) + D \cdot \nabla^2 G^{(1)}(t, r_0; s), \quad (33)$$

$$\partial_t G^{(i)}(t, r_0; s) = \lambda^{(i)}(G^{(1)}(t, r_0; s) - G^{(i)}(t, r_0; s)), \quad (34)$$

with drift and diffusion coefficients given by

$$C = Q_S (dx_0(p_x - \tilde{p}_x), dy_0(p_y - \tilde{p}_y), dz_0(p_z - \tilde{p}_z)). \quad (35)$$

$$D = \frac{1}{2} Q_S (dx_0^2(p_x + \tilde{p}_x), dy_0^2(p_y + \tilde{p}_y), dz_0^2(p_z + \tilde{p}_z)). \quad (36)$$

4. CONCLUSIONS

The work discusses a discrete branching random walk algorithm on lattice domains which models the diffusion of neutrons in a reaction domain with absorbing boundary conditions. Analyzing expectation and variance of the total number of neutrons we observed agreement between solutions of partial difference equations with Monte Carlo simulations. Eq. (11) gives the criticality condition where the parameter α can be interpreted as the no-escape probability. An explicit calculation of the second moment allows for the variance reduction strategy presented in Eq. (21). The simplicity of lattice-based models also provides insight into the neutron population behavior in diffusive systems, allowing for simulations even when the time-homogeneous assumption doesn't hold, such as during fuel burnup.

Lastly, we establish a bridge between the continuous and discrete representations. Note that if the system is isotropic $p_j = \tilde{p}_j$, the drift coefficient vanishes $C = 0$, and the standard diffusion approximation found in [4] is recovered. Also, note that in a purely diffusive process with $C = 0$, if the diffusion constant D is known then a diffusion process in continuous domains can be arbitrary approximated by a branching random walk which uses only four canonical directions. In this case, it is only necessary to increase the space-time mesh resolution.

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